

DiSSCo Transition Project

**Translation of lessons learned from BICIKL
into the DiSSCo context**

Work Package 2 - Milestone 13

Marko Lovric, CETAF

Ana Casino, CETAF

Grant number 101130121

HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01-02 — Early phase implementation of ESFRI Projects
which entered the ESFRI Roadmap in 2018

HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions - Horizon Europe

25 July 2024

Version 1.0 final**Table of contents**

List of abbreviations	5
List of figures	5
1. Introduction	6
2. BiCIKL's approach to training provision and lessons learned	7
2.1. User-centred design	7
2.2. Service providers as key contributors	8
2.3. Lessons learned and recommendations from BKH	10
3. Translating lessons learned from BiCIKL to DiSSCo context	13
4. Conclusion	18
5. References	19

Project DiSSCo Transition**Grant Agreement n°** 101130121**Start of the project** 01 December 2023**Duration** 18 months**Project Coordinator** Stichting Naturalis Biodiversity Center

Translation of lessons learned from

Milestone title BICIKL into the DiSSCo
context**Milestone n°** 13**Means of verification** Report**Work Package** 2**Lead Beneficiary** CETAF**Due date of milestone** 30 June 2024**Actual submission date** 25 July 2024**Quality review** No**Milestone status**

Version	Status	Date	Responsible	Actions
0.1	Draft	07/06/2024	Marko Lovric	Sent for internal review
0.2	Draft 0.1 review	10/06/2024	Ana Casino Marko Lovric	Reviewed
0.3	Draft 0.2 review	12/06/2024	Ana Casino Marko Lovric Judite Alves Eri Antaloudaki	Finalised, with incorporation of feedback from task partners
1.0	Final	25/07/2024	Marko Lovric	Submitted

Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Executive Summary

This milestone, MS13, is intended as a report highlighting approaches and ideas adopted by the Biodiversity Community Integrated Knowledge Library (BiCIKL)¹ project when developing the training materials for Biodiversity Knowledge Hub (BKH) users that could also be relevant in the DiSSCo context. Having already finalised its training programme necessary for using the BKH, the BiCIKL project developed and implemented specific recommendations for guiding the construction of the courses in the Moodle platform. In this report, we take the key recommendations and guiding principles from BiCIKL and elaborate on how they can be applied when building the first layer of the DiSSCo Helpdesk supporting materials. Special attention is dedicated to two foundational aspects of training applied in BiCIKL – user-centred design of training materials and service providers' contributing mechanisms.

Keywords

Helpdesk, research infrastructure, training, user needs, FAIR

¹ <https://doi.org/10.3030/101007492>

List of abbreviations

BiCIKL – Biodiversity Community Integrated Knowledge Library

BKH – Biodiversity Knowledge Hub

CA - Consortium Agreement

D - Deliverable

DiSSCo - Distributed System of Scientific Collections

DTP - DiSSCo Transition Project

FAIR – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable

GA - Grant Agreement

MS - Milestone

RFC - Request For Comments

RI - Research Infrastructure

WP - Work Package

List of figures

Figure 1 - Main identified user groups of BKH and use cases for each one of them (pg.7)

Figure 2 - Key questions for building well-structured use cases (pg.9)

Figure 3 – BKH Best Practices to guide the development of the training material (pg. 11)

Figure 4 - First layer of support (blue box) in the overall DiSSCo Helpdesk workflow (pg. 12)

1. Introduction

Biodiversity Community Integrated Knowledge Library (BiCIKL) was a project aiming to create a new user community of biodiversity data, tools and services, interlinked under the FAIR principles and gathered around a single knowledge portal – the Biodiversity Knowledge Hub (BKH). The portal provides unprecedented access to data and services linking specimens, genomics, observations, taxonomy and publications to a large variety of biodiversity and life sciences stakeholders, ranging from researchers to citizen scientists. As such, the successful usage of this resource and consequently the growth of the user community depend on a well-developed and thought-out system of training materials enabling smooth tooling up of new BKH users. For this purpose, a lot of time and effort was dedicated during BiCIKL to the development of a training programme that can serve as the introduction to the BKH, but also demonstrate some more in-depth uses of certain services offered under BKH.

Led by CETAF, the work in BiCIKL dedicated to building the training resources (Task T2.3) produced a Moodle-based training programme containing two large training modules, using new and existing materials, that can be freely accessed by anyone, from anywhere and at any time. As a joint effort among BiCIKL partners, this training programme was developed on top of many different components arising from the project and its various services, and can thus become a tested example and a source of inspiration for DiSSCo due to certain similarities between the two infrastructures. This can be done by identifying the lessons learned arising from the construction of the BKH training programme and applying them to DiSSCo, focusing specifically on the first layer of the DiSSCo Helpdesk. This first layer of the DiSSCo Helpdesk collectively refers to the components belonging to the first line of support provided to the user of the DiSSCo Research Infrastructure (RI), or the self-service part of the overall DiSSCo workflow. Namely, it will contain the FAQs and all the supporting documentation aiming to equip the users with the basic knowledge needed to successfully access and use the services DiSSCo will provide. Other layers will need to be developed at a later stage to respond to users' needs in terms of technical performance and upgrade (second layer) that will link to the platform developer and maintenance provider which will then provide feedback to users. A further developed and more detailed layer (third layer) will directly link to the provider of the service as the ultimate reliable source of information to back up the usage of the service itself. As such, many of the best practices followed in the development of the BKH training programme remain relevant when planning the aforementioned first line of support for DiSSCo and can be translated into the DiSSCo context.

In order to do so, we will first look at the approach the BiCIKL community has adopted for the purpose of developing training materials and highlight the key lessons learned from that process (Chapter 2). We will then apply these lessons learned to the circumstances in the DiSSCo Research Infrastructure (RI) and provide specific recommendations to consider for the upcoming development DiSSCo's own corpus of training materials and guidelines gathered under the Helpdesk (Chapter 3).

2. BiCIKL's approach to training provision and lessons learned

2.1. User-centred design

As the BKH is a one-stop portal built from scratch, its user community did not fully develop at the time of its construction. This adds a significant challenge to the task of creating a training programme for the tooling up of the users² since the team had clearly defined the user groups prior to their active participation in BKH. Therefore, it was necessary to devote ample focus to user requirements and needs while designing the training needed by those groups to facilitate the use of the BKH. In this regard, there were two key sources of information related to the user needs: the user requirements analysis conducted in WP1 and a dedicated workshop on the users' training needs organised in the framework of Task 2.3.

The user requirements analysis, presented in deliverable D1.1 (Arvanitidis et al, 2022)³, aimed to determine the users' needs for different dimensions comprising types of data, quality of data, and modes of access. The BiCIKL partners carefully designed an online questionnaire to collect the appropriate information from the broader community, including BiCIKL partnership and external stakeholders from publishers to other Research Infrastructures. Subsequently, this information was converted to data and finally, a thorough analysis was applied to find potential patterns and infer the processes behind the patterns. A total of 72 responses were collected from the members of the targeted community, providing valuable first-hand insights from the future users.

Figure 1: Main identified user groups of BKH and use cases for each one of them.

² Researchers, libraries, publishers, digitization technology providers, digital repositories, research institutions, and public authorities

³ Arvanitidis, C., Huertas Olivares, C., Groom, Q., Bamford, E., Vaira, L., Montinaro, S., Casino, A., Agosti, D., Barov, B., Hristova, K., Penev, L. (2022). User requirements analysis report. Deliverable D1.1 EU Horizon 2020 BiCIKL Project, Grant Agreement No 101007492.

In order to clearly conceptualise the BKH training programme and the methodologies to be used for its construction, there was a need to first define the necessary parameters of this programme, such as audience, scope, format, functionalities, and a sustainability model. On the other hand, it was likewise important to ensure that the contents truly correspond to the needs of the users required for effectively accessing and using the BKH in the simplest and most effective manner, as well as making full use of the publishing tools and workflows. For these purposes, a workshop was organised early in the process within T2.3, in collaboration with partners, to address primarily the following questions together with the BiCIKL community and to ensure broad endorsement of the platform by as many involved actors as possible:

- How will the training platform be integrated within the BKH website?
- What audiences should be targeted by the training programme?
- What should be the scope of the training programme (going beyond T2.3)?
- Which format(s) would be most suitable for translating the specific content developed by the related tasks?
- How to ensure the sustainability of the training platform once the BKH is fully operational?
- How will the BKH training be linked to the training content of BiCIKL's RIs?

The outcomes of the workshop proved to be critical to the success of the training programme as they highlighted several important recommendations arising from the discussion:

- a) Content scope. First of all, it was established that the approach to learning needs to be defined in terms of addressing different levels of proficiency, i.e. generic offer vs granularity.
- b) User competencies. Following this, one must consider different levels of knowledge across the community and, in terms of more novel tools and methods (such as data liberation), we should strive to make something progressive, allowing for a step-by-step approach to accommodate various readiness levels.
- c) Supporting resources. Likewise, in order to maximise user-friendliness, the training materials should include practical examples and use cases that will highlight the context of the use of each service as well as the challenges that the use of the service poses to the users.
- d) Services identification. Finally, it was agreed that the services-driven approach would simplify the training framework definition. Therefore, different services built under BiCIKL should list their tools and mechanisms, as well as a series of case studies to facilitate the training process.

2.2. Service providers as key contributors

On the other side from users are the providers of services, tools and data that the BKH portal gathers and interlinks. At the time of writing this report, there are twelve different

services integrated into the BKH, provided by the different RIs who participated in the BiCIKL project. The providers themselves possess the most suitable expertise to showcase the use of their services and demonstrate the added value of linking them with other products. It was therefore understood that these RIs must be involved in the design of the training, sharing best practices and highlighting the practical challenges that users are likely to experience.

The analysis of the BKH services and the definition of their key characteristics was the reference point for the design of the practical use cases aiming to enrich users' understanding of the context of using the various services as well as the challenges they will face during their implementation. For this reason, a 'use case' section was added to the guide for each service. In most cases, a detailed scenario of use was considered complementary to help users during the training process.

The report compiling the BKH Best Practices⁴ was produced and the related recommendations were the reference point for the development of the training materials and the overall organisation of the BKH training programme. The Best Practices and the population of the related Best Practices Document Template (BPDT) offered a unique opportunity for BKH users to engage in real-life situations, and to provide them with a relatable and highly relevant learning experience. It is expected that this immersive approach creates a highly engaging situation for them.

The information provided by the service providers was organised in such a way as to provide the context of use, the research needs that are being met by each service, the service added value to the daily practices of the target groups, and the expected qualitative upgrade the use of the service offers to biodiversity research. Furthermore, an exemplary scenario of use is presented along with the skills and competencies that are necessary for the use of each service. In cases where the service was considered as rather demanding the course materials were enriched with further resources, tutorials, videos, or even recommendations for focused courses on the use of specific tools and applications. Figure 2 presents the structure used to develop each of the use cases.

⁴ Arvanitidis C, Sotiriou S, Huertas Olivares C, Lovrić M, Vallo C, Casino A (2023). Biodiversity Knowledge Hub Best Practices communicated to T2.3. BiCIKL Milestone MS12 EU Horizon 2020 BiCIKL Project, Grant Agreement No 101007492.

Use Case for Each Service	
Context of Use	<i>Why should users use your service?</i>
	<i>What does it do?</i>
Meeting the research community's needs	<i>What needs/challenges for the research community does it respond to?</i>
Service Added Value	<i>What is its added value?</i>
Competitive Advantages of the Service	<i>Why is your solution better than the competing solutions, if any?</i>
Qualitative Upgrade to Biodiversity Research	<i>Why does the specific service provide a qualitative upgrade on the current use of biodiversity data?</i>
Exemplary Scenario of Use	<i>How the service can be used? Featured data use - exemplary use of the service</i>
Users' Skills	<i>What are the scientific and IT competencies required to effectively use your service?</i>
Users' Challenges	<i>What challenges do you envisage users may face in using your service?</i>
Users' role and potential contributions	<i>Do you envisage a role for users to take part in the long-term development of your service (i.e., feedback gathering for service improvement)?</i>

Figure 2: Key questions for building well-structured use cases

The provision of Best Practices and recommendations has facilitated the creation of numerous realistic scenarios that potential BKH users can use to formulate, study, and test a variety of situations they could face in their practice. The use cases describe instances or situations that biodiversity practitioners recognise as familiar and likely to occur in their research. This brings relevance to the training which makes it memorable. Realistic use cases (directly related to the user requirements) offer the chance to solve problems and to practise possible situations they might face. It prepares users with one or more appropriate responses, making those more effective in practical terms while also boosting the confidence of users in their usage. In this framework, it is expected that the use cases will offer a qualitative upgrade to the training materials of BKH.

2.3. Lessons learned and recommendations from BKH

Based on the elements explored above, the BKH Training Programme report (D2.3)⁵ puts forward several concrete guidelines and recommendations in relation to developing the BKH training materials. While specifically addressing the BKH and its services, many of these could be replicated in the DiSSCo context, which is the main focus of this report.

Below is the summary of these recommendations, taken directly from the deliverable:

Set clear educational goals

⁵ Sotiriou, S., Casino, A. & Lovrić, M. (2023). BiCKL training programme MOOC. Deliverable D2.3 EU Horizon 2020 BiCKL Project, Grant Agreement No 101007492.

The first step of the process is to reflect on both participant and provider objectives and to set them clearly. Providers need to decide on the real purpose behind creating a web-based course in the first place. The end goal here should be to educate and share knowledge in an accessible way. What exactly do you want participants to know about the BKH and its services by the end of the course or by the end of the specific module? It may also be worthwhile to check what else is available in the field and what resources you will need to fulfil this project.

? Determine the target audience

Another fundamental step is to specify the target audience. One method of achieving this is by creating a user persona. What do they need? What might their learning outcomes be? It may also be worth considering their demographics. Figure 1 presents the key needs and interests of the main BKH user groups. Providers must make sure that their courses and materials are fully aligned with the user's needs.

? Bring in experts

To ensure that your course is a resounding success, you will now want to consult experts in the field. Subject matter expert (SME) is both primary sources of information and idea generators for e-learning course developers. They will help you create learning objectives, provide content on specific topics, and validate and enrich course material. Remember, without real expertise, it is unlikely the course will be valuable to learners. Meanwhile, Instructional Designers (IDs) can help provide this expertise to learners in a fruitful way, making sure learning outcomes are reached. SMEs and IDs must work well together to meet your educational vision.

? Design the course structure

Before jumping into production, it is crucial to create the course structure. That means elaborating the structure (usually 7-10 course modules), the key concepts, and deciding how you will deliver the information. This certainly simplifies the task, offering guidelines on videos, quizzes, discussion boards, polls, etc. This ensures cohesion all around the board, which is surely helpful for your students. Just bear in mind your target audience and learning outcomes throughout this process as discussed above.

? Assemble the information

Here, you need to create all your presentation materials, whether text, photos, icons, graphics, infographic content, or animations. You will then put all these materials together to summarise the course succinctly. This can be done via a storyboard or a PowerPoint presentation.

? Prepare a short introductory video

To optimally engage the users, effective video content is needed. Video helps your content be more engaging as it conveys tone and emotion more effectively than written text. As is often the case, first go back to your initial goal. Remind yourself of your target audience, what the learning outcomes are, and what your purpose is in creating them. More practically, it is about creating an engaging and captivating narrative.

Select the most appropriate Use Case

An exemplary scenario of use is presented along with the skills and competencies that are necessary for the realisation of the different tasks proposed by the training materials. In cases where the tasks are rather demanding the course materials could be enriched with further resources, tutorials, videos, or even recommendations for focused courses on the use of specific tools and applications. It is important to relate the use case content with the introductory video and discuss the context of use and the challenges of each module of the course.

Gather feedback

You are now ready to release the course to the audience. Now is the time to check for any teaching inadequacies, taking a look at the overall cohesion of your course and measuring the consistency and balance of the modules. Get feedback from the users! This is a sure-fire way to find out what worked well and what needs to be improved.

Apart from these specific recommendations, the previously mentioned BKH Best Practices document establishes 10 best practices, which are useful principles complementing the above recommendations (Figure 3).

1. **Keep it simple:** a simple structure helps the user to navigate better
2. **Make it informative:** all available information should be discoverable easily and efficiently and by multiple means
3. Explain **why the user should make use** of the services available
4. Provide information on **how to get started and proceed**
5. **Guide the users to collaborate** and make use of the resources available collectively – start from simple questions towards the more complex ones
6. **Provide pre-set queries** and ways to find information and answers
7. Early and continued **focus on users' requirements**
8. **Empirical knowledge:** learn and adapt from the users' reactions, comments, and performance to be observed and measured, to identify problems and errors. Feedback must be sought and incorporated into the services available
9. **Iterative approach:** improvements should be re-tested
10. **Communicate the successful use and results** of the BKH

Figure 3: BKH Best Practices to guide the development of the training material

These principles are of cross-cutting nature and can be applied to multiple guidelines proposed above, ensuring consistent and well-designed work across the board.

3. Translating lessons learned from BiCIKL to DiSSCo context

Having looked at the key recommendations arising from the BiCIKL project in relation to developing a user-oriented and sustainable support system for the users of the BKH, it is now time to apply them to DiSSCo Research Infrastructure. While the two infrastructures are not conceptually the same (in fact, DiSSCo is one of the RIs integrated into the BKH), there are certain similarities which make it possible to translate many of the lessons learned in BiCIKL to the context of the DiSSCo Helpdesk. Specifically, we are referring here to the first layer of the Helpdesk, providing capacity-building resources to the new users of the DiSSCo RI. This first layer of support is envisioned as a corpus of support documentation and FAQs to facilitate understanding, access and exploitation of DiSSCo RI from the user perspective, as can be seen in Figure 4 (“self-services”).

Figure 4: First layer of support (blue box) in the overall DiSSCo Helpdesk workflow⁶

In this regard, this supporting documentation provided by the DiSSCo Helpdesk is relatively similar to the documentation collated and integrated in the BKH training programme. The key idea here is then to take the well-established and tested guidelines from the BKH context and apply them to the DiSSCo context. We will do so by mapping each of the BKH guidelines indicated in Chapter 2 above against the current situation in DiSSCo. Furthermore, in order to enhance the quality and user-friendliness of the materials, we have applied for each of the recommendations for DiSSCo the validated BKH

⁶ Alves, J., Bellucci L., Berger, F., Casino, A., Figueira, R., Innocenti, G., Tilley, L. (2023). Recommendations on the Helpdesk and user support services. Deliverable D2.2 EU Horizon 2020 DiSSCo Prepare Project, Grant Agreement No 871043.

guiding principles (see Figure 3) which can be appropriate in that specific DiSSCo situation. The applicable best practices are listed underneath each recommendation and should be taken into consideration when producing the DiSSCo supporting resources for the Helpdesk.

Recommendation	DiSSCo context
Set clear educational goals	This recommendation, while somewhat self-explanatory, is important because the DiSSCo is such a complex and multifaceted ecosystem. This is the moment to check that the educational goals are aligned with the reality on the ground. Understanding the capacity building required for each DiSSCo service will ensure that the resources are properly allocated and that the scope of the educational material is fit for purpose. Ultimately, a key question to answer is: what level of knowledge should this material provide?
<p>Applicable BPs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Explain why the user should make use of the services available 5. Guide the users to collaborate and make use of the resources available collectively – start from simple questions towards the more complex ones 7. Early and continued focus on users' requirements 8. Empirical knowledge: learn and adapt from the users' reactions, comments, and performance to be observed and measured, to identify problems and errors. Feedback must be sought and incorporated into the services available 	
Recommendation	DiSSCo context
Determine the target audience	Setting up a comprehensive support system depends on knowing the user base. While the rich variety of different user profiles in infrastructures like the BKH and DiSSCo is a very welcome situation, it also means a more complex mapping of the target audience. While in BKH this meant identifying the main user profiles and determining the various potential uses, in DiSSCo this might be more linked to the services themselves. On the other hand, we must also not forget that services will not work in isolation and their certain user types will be making use of multiple DiSSCo services.
<p>Applicable BPs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Explain why the user should make use of the services available 5. Guide the users to collaborate and make use of the resources available collectively – start from simple questions towards the more complex ones 	

7. Early and continued focus on users' requirements	
Recommendation	DiSSCo context
Bring in experts	Another crucial component is the direct involvement of experts in the design of the supporting material, meaning both the 'subject matter experts' (most likely the service providers themselves) and 'instructional designers' (people experienced in creating compelling and user-friendly educational content). In the DiSSCo context, this is especially important due to the amount of different concepts that will need to be presented in a 'digestible' manner, so this type of collaboration is recommended from an early stage.
<p>Applicable BPs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Make it informative: all available information should be discoverable easily and efficiently and by multiple means 3. Explain why the user should make use of the services available 5. Guide the users to collaborate and make use of the resources available collectively – start from simple questions towards the more complex ones 6. Provide pre-set queries and ways to find information and answers 	
Recommendation	DiSSCo context
Design the course structure	While the DiSSCo Helpdesk will not necessarily provide courses, the logic of this recommendation can still be applied to DiSSCo. This pertains mostly to how the information is organised and how different methods are used to deliver it in an interactive way. Certain educational tools might be more suitable for specific segments, while others might work better in different contexts. Learning outcomes and target audience are key factors in this regard.
<p>Applicable BPs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Keep it simple: a simple structure helps the user to navigate better 2. Make it informative: all available information should be discoverable easily and efficiently and by multiple means 4. Provide information on how to get started and proceed 5. Guide the users to collaborate and make use of the resources available collectively – start from simple questions towards the more complex ones 6. Provide pre-set queries and ways to find information and answers 	

- 8. **Empirical knowledge:** learn and adapt from the users' reactions, comments, and performance to be observed and measured, to identify problems and errors. Feedback must be sought and incorporated into the services available
- 9. **Iterative approach:** improvements should be re-tested

Recommendation	DiSSCo context
----------------	----------------

Assemble the information	A vast amount of information generated by the DiSSCo community means that one should avoid excessive 'walls of text' and generally overly descriptive explanations for delivering it to the users. Instead, a mix of media (photos, text boxes, animations, infographics, etc.) can be used to stimulate the audience.
---------------------------------	--

- Applicable BPs:**
- 1. **Keep it simple:** a simple structure helps the user to navigate better
 - 2. **Make it informative:** all available information should be discoverable easily and efficiently and by multiple means
 - 4. Provide information on **how to get started and proceed**
 - 6. **Provide pre-set queries** and ways to find information and answers
 - 7. Early and continued **focus on users' requirements**
 - 8. **Empirical knowledge:** learn and adapt from the users' reactions, comments, and performance to be observed and measured, to identify problems and errors. Feedback must be sought and incorporated into the services available

Recommendation	DiSSCo context
----------------	----------------

Prepare a short introductory video	As an already tried and tested method, a short video can truly transform a learning module and significantly improve the engagement of the users. It also provides an opportunity to grab the attention of the audience at the very start of the process, giving them a rundown of the key features of a service and the expected outcomes of the educational materials. This could be especially applicable in DiSSCo given the range of complex concepts and innovations gathered under it.
---	---

- Applicable BPs:**
- 2. **Make it informative:** all available information should be discoverable easily and efficiently and by multiple means
 - 3. Explain **why the user should make use** of the services available
 - 7. Early and continued **focus on users' requirements**

Recommendation	DiSSCo context
Select the most appropriate Use Case	<p>Just as is the case with the BKH, the DiSSCo RI will have a multitude of use cases, with new ones probably arising in the future. For the purposes of the Helpdesk, it would be beneficial to select those that are both easy to understand but that are suitable for demonstrating the added value of a particular service or the RI as a whole. Many new users learn best when presented with real-life practical applications, which is why the selected use cases should resonate with a wide range of stakeholders.</p>
<p>Applicable BPs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Keep it simple: a simple structure helps the user to navigate better 2. Make it informative: all available information should be discoverable easily and efficiently and by multiple means 3. Explain why the user should make use of the services available 7. Early and continued focus on users' requirements 8. Empirical knowledge: learn and adapt from the users' reactions, comments, and performance to be observed and measured, to identify problems and errors. Feedback must be sought and incorporated into the services available 9. Iterative approach: improvements should be re-tested 	
Recommendation	DiSSCo context
Gather feedback	<p>The DiSSCo Helpdesk will need to continuously evolve as the catalogue of services grows and the services themselves go through improvements. In this regard, feedback will be a key tool for making sure that the support given matches the changing reality on the ground. As such, the Helpdesk will certainly profit from establishing a robust feedback system from the very start of its operation.</p>
<p>Applicable BPs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Make it informative: all available information should be discoverable easily and efficiently and by multiple means 3. Explain why the user should make use of the services available 4. Provide information on how to get started and proceed 5. Guide the users to collaborate and make use of the resources available collectively – start from simple questions towards the more complex ones 6. Provide pre-set queries and ways to find information and answers 7. Early and continued focus on users' requirements 	

8. **Empirical knowledge:** learn and adapt from the users' reactions, comments, and performance to be observed and measured, to identify problems and errors. Feedback must be sought and incorporated into the services available
9. **Iterative approach:** improvements should be re-tested

All the above considerations should be taken into account when elaborating training material, guidelines and other resources to facilitate implementation and use of the different services to be provided by DiSSCo.

The distributed nature of DiSSCo RI makes the scope of the Helpdesk complex and diverse. Its complexity derives from the services integrated in the RI that are either core or complementary to its full operation, and on the other hand, the provision of the services will come from a variety of sources (and providers) which may incorporate distinct approaches. Those aspects will strongly influence the necessity of a comprehensive Helpdesk that can serve a diversity of users from the scientific community and beyond.

Currently, at the time of this report, the different services are at a varied levels of readiness and completion. Those are together aiming at supporting and enabling both physical and digital access to natural history collections held at the partners of the RI, but not only. DiSSCo envisages to provide support to scale up digitisation of the collections and contribute with new tools and mechanisms to the enhancement of the interpretation, curation, annotation and use of the data contained in the collections.

To that end, a large set of services are required, many of which are still in development and are expected to be ready and operational by when the DiSSCo RI starts its full functioning, i.e in 2026. All those are listed in the DiSSCo website⁷ but such a list may be enlarged as the construction of DiSSCo progresses and new needs are detected and covered with new solutions.

4. Conclusion

Building the DiSSCo Helpdesk is a challenging endeavour due to the range of services envisaged under the RI, as well as the variety of user types that are likely to be using them. Each service comes with its own specificities, meaning that supporting materials to be developed might differ in their design. They will need to be fit for purpose, accessible yet comprehensive and compelling enough to keep the users engaged. Significant effort has already been invested into analysing the different aspects of the DiSSCo Helpdesk in previous projects, such as DiSSCo Prepare⁸ (Task T2.3), but the BiCIKL project also provides some important lessons learned in this regard. Having already finalised its training programme (akin to DiSSCo's first layer of support) necessary for using the BKH, the BiCIKL project developed and implemented specific recommendations for guiding the

⁷ <https://www.dissco.eu/services/>

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.3030/871043>

construction of the courses in a Moodle platform. As we can see from this report, many of these recommendations are very much valid when translated into the DiSSCo context.

Therefore, this document can be used to feed further development of the Helpdesk, especially in its early phase of development, given that it highlights the importance of involving the experts from the start and placing the user needs at the centre of the equation.

5. References

Arvanitidis, C., Huertas Olivares, C., Groom, Q., Bamford, E., Vaira, L., Montinaro, S., Casino, A., Agosti, D., Barov, B., Hristova, K., Penev, L. (2022). *User requirements analysis report. Deliverable D1.1 EU Horizon 2020 BiCIKL Project*, Grant Agreement No 101007492.

Arvanitidis C, Sotiriou S, Huertas Olivares C, Lovrić M, Vallo C, Casino A (2023). *Biodiversity Knowledge Hub Best Practices communicated to T2.3. BiCIKL Milestone MS12 EU Horizon 2020 BiCIKL Project*, Grant Agreement No 101007492.

Sotiriou, S., Casino, A. & Lovrić, M. (2023). *BiCKL training programme MOOC. Deliverable D2.3 EU Horizon 2020 BiCIKL Project*, Grant Agreement No 101007492.

Alves, J., Bellucci L., Berger, F., Casino, A., Figueira, R., Innocenti, G., Tilley, L. (2023). *Recommendations on the Helpdesk and user support services. Deliverable D2.2 EU Horizon 2020 DiSSCo Prepare Project*, Grant Agreement No 871043.